

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND WORK MOTIVATION OF GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES**Macauyag, Datunor S.**

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine which domain of organizational commitment best predicts work motivation of government employees. The researchers used descriptive correlation method which includes a survey conducted with 120 government employees as participants. The adopted questionnaires which the respondents were asked to answer have been presented and validated. Mean, Pearson-r Correlation and Linear Regression were the statistical tools used in this research. The findings of the study revealed that government employees disclosed high level of organizational commitment and work motivation. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between organizational commitments and work motivation of government employees. Furthermore, organizational commitment significantly influences work motivation. Continuance commitment as domain of organizational commitment can singly influence work motivation.

Keywords:

Organizational Commitment, Continuance Commitment, Normative Commitment, Work Motivation, Work-Interest, Motivation by Income, Motivation by Drive, Government Employees, Davao City, Philippines,

INTRODUCTION

Employees often feel not being valued because the management is not providing them a necessary support and assets to attain productivity. Those who punched the clock, bides his time at the office, is likely to be unmotivated and is excited to punch out at the end of the day, is usually not the best employee. An unmotivated employee does not seem to care if he has a job or not. This employee doesn't feel sorry for being late and he doesn't seem to jump in to work with any level of positivism (Lister, 2003).

Moreover, work motivation is an important element in determining employees' productivity and efficiency. It is a critical aspect at the workplace which leads to the performance of the department and even the company. Motivating employees needs to be a regular routine (Crabtree, 2013). If employees are motivated, they are willing to exert efforts towards the accomplishment of their goal. A motivated workforce resulted high productivity which helps business goals.

Connection between organizational commitment and work motivation must not be disregarded. These two are closely related and it can impact on productivity, creativity, and loyalty of the employees (Odembo, 2013). Previous studies on organizational commitment have shown that employees with higher organizational commitment engage in organizational behavior and this, in turn, results in better performance and higher work motivation that are beneficial to the organization (Alimohamaddi & Neyshabor, et al, 2013). The above scenario prompted the researchers to conduct the study.

Background Information

Employees often feel not being valued because the management is not providing them a necessary support and assets to attain productivity. Those who punched the clock, bides his time at the office, is likely to be unmotivated and is excited to punch out at the end of the day, is usually not the best employee. An unmotivated employee does not seem to care if he has a job or not. This employee doesn't feel sorry for being late and he doesn't seem to jump in to work with any level of positivism (Lister, 2003).

While acting upon this problem through counter measures, it is still important to discover and find the underlying factors of Organizational Commitment and Work Motivation of Government Employees. For that, this research was conducted.

Purpose of the study

The study was conducted to determine which domain of organizational commitment best predicts the work motivation of government employees.

Research questions

1. Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire. Rate from 1 to 5
2. I have chosen a work to attain certain input objectives. Rate from 1 to 5
3. I work to earn money. Rate from 1 to 5

Literature review

Affective Commitment. There is a pool of options on how much an employee actually likes or feels as part of an organization. Its effect on employee can result to their performance, commitment or may harm the organization by criticizing it in their social circles because its base is on their personal subjectivity. Affective commitment is when the gap between individual values and organizational values is minimal. However, the congruence between individual values and organizational values in employees can also be built and enhanced by strategies and programs to enhance employee understanding and recognition of organizational values (Orife, et al, 2010).

Continuance Commitment is an employee's commitment to continuance affected by the factors driven by organizational culture. When an employee finds an organization to be positive and supportive, he/she will have a higher degree of continuance commitment. Important organizational factors like employee loyalty and employee retention are components of continuance commitment (Orife, et al, 2010).

Normative Commitment is higher in organizations that value loyalty and systematically communicate the fact to employees with rewards, incentives and other strategies. Same is also true when employees regularly see visible examples of the employer being committed to employee's well-being. High levels of job satisfaction, in turn, reduces employee turnover and increases the organization's ability to recruit and retain talent (Orife, et al, 2010).

Work Motivation by Interest. Interest and motivation are of central importance to educational psychologists, because they denote phenomena that are said to mediate cognition and learning, and therefore individual development (Roth and Hsu, 2008).

Work Motivation by Income. Money is an effective, powerful and simple motivator. Self-evidently, money motivates and extra money motivates people to work extra hard. It's natural to compete, and when rewarded with money for better work then productivity and standards are raised for all. Further, because it is not always wise or indeed possible to promote individuals, money can be used as an equitable and very acceptable way to reward all workers. More important, because money is a generalized reinforcer it is always acceptable to all people everywhere and at all times. Money talks, and it talks loudly and clearly (Furnham, 2012).

Work Motivation by Drive. Individual's personal drive is often the starting point of motivation. This drive helps individuals focus on specific goals they wish to achieve or how they wish to improve their life. All people

have some level of personal drive. They may focus their personal drive on obtaining educational degrees, building a family or starting a business. Personal drive may be enhanced by the extrinsic motivational factors found in the goals individuals are attempting to achieve (Vitez, 2018).

Work Motivation by Self. Self-motivation is a power that drives us to keep moving ahead. It encourages continuous learning and success, whatever be the scenario. Self-motivation is a primary means of realizing our goals and progressing. It is basically related to our inventiveness in setting dynamic goals for ourselves, and our faith that we possess the required skills and competencies for achieving those challenging goals. We often feel the need for self-motivation (Juneja, 2008)

Methodology

The researchers used descriptive correlation method. This method is appropriate in determining the relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation of government employees. There were 120 respondents in the survey conducted by the researchers. Questionnaires for organizational commitment and work motivation were adopted. The adopted questionnaires were personally given to the respondents by the researchers. The survey conducted is compliant to the research survey ethics protocol which reserved the confidentiality of the personal information of the participants.

Data Collection Methods

The study used questionnaires for organizational commitment and work motivation. The adopted questionnaires were personally given to the respondents by the researchers and duly accomplished by the respondents

Data Analysis

The researchers used descriptive correlation method of study. This method is appropriate in determining the relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation of government employees. There were 120 respondents in the survey conducted by the researchers. Questionnaires for organizational commitment were answerable by scale of 1 to 5 in which 5 indicates as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as seldom and 1 as never. Meanwhile, the questionnaires for work motivation were also answerable by the scale of 1 to 5 in which 5 indicates as strongly agree, 4 as agree, 3 as undecided, 2 as disagree and 1 as strongly disagree.

Discussion of Findings**Level of Organizational Commitment among Government Employees**

Presented in Table 1 is the level of organizational commitment of government employees and they revealed high with the mean rating of 3.55. Moreover, they disclosed high level in terms of affective commitment and continuance commitment with mean ratings of 3.79 and 3.79 respectively. This means that in general, the employees are highly committed in their organization because they have a sense of belongingness and emotional attachment. Further, they revealed moderate level in terms of normative commitment with the mean ratings of 3.45. It sometimes proves that every employee, loyalty is more of a personal value rather than organizational and normative commitment depends on personal meaning.

This finding affirms with the statement of Anderson et al (2010) indicated that affective commitment is directly proportional to positive work experience which could be personal or individual experience. Moreover, continuance commitment shows that even though how stressful the work is, but the fear of leaving and not getting any job right after could lead to cataclysm.

Table 1 Level of Organizational Commitment of Government Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive level
Affective Commitment	.58	3.79	High
Continuance Commitment	.58	3.79	High
Normative Commitment	.49	3.45	Moderate
Overall	.45	3.55	High

Level of Work Motivation of Government Employees

Presented in Table 2 is the level of work motivation of government employees and they showed high level with a mean rating of 4.21. This indicates that government employees are often motivated in working, and most of them consider personal objective as goal like they want to be proud of themselves, earn money and want to learn new things. Moreover, they revealed high level for interest and enjoyment with the mean rating of 4.20; motivation by income with 4.23; motivation by drive with 4.36 and motivation by self with 4.02 respectively. This finding corroborates with the statement of Heathfield (2018) that the reasons for working are as individual as the person. But, all people work because the workplace provides what they needed. Through their organizations, they are able to attain their goals and objectives in life.

Table 2 Level of Work Motivation of Government Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive level
Workers Interest and Enjoyment	.58	4.20	High
Motivation by income	.61	4.23	High
Motivation by Drive	.56	4.36	High
Motivation by self	.48	4.02	High
Overall	.45	4.21	High

Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Work Motivation of Government Employees

Presented in Table 3 is the relationship between organizational commitments and work motivation of government employees as reveal in r- value of .270** with the P value of .003 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that organizational commitment of government employees has to do with their work motivation. Affective commitment and continuance commitment significantly related to work motivation as disclosed in the r - values of .419** and 0.419** respectively. Their corresponding p - values are lesser than .05 level of

significance. The result is significant and the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies further that the higher is the affective and continuance commitments, the higher is the work motivation.

This finding affirms with the statement of Odembo (2013) that connection between organizational commitment and work motivation must not be disregarded. These two are closely related and it can impact on productivity, creativity, and loyalty of the employees.

Table 3 Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Work Motivation of Government Employees

Organizational Commitment	Work Motivation				
	Enjoyment	Income	Drive	Self	Overall
Affective Commitment	.468** (.000)	.158 (.084)	.284** (.002)	.453** (.000)	.419** (.000)
Continuance Commitment	.468** (.000)	.158 (.084)	.284** (.002)	.453** (.000)	.419** (.000)
Normative Commitment	.167 (.068)	-.010 (.912)	.065 (.484)	.198* (.030)	.129 (.159)
Overall	.323** (.000)	.057 (.536)	.151 (.100)	.355** (.000)	.270** (.003)

** Significant at .01

* Significant at .05

Domain of Organizational Commitment that Best Predict Work Motivation of Government Employees

Presented in Table 4 is the domain of organizational commitment best predicts the work motivation of government employees. Continuance commitment as domain revealed a t- value of 4.75 with the p – value of .000 which says lesser of 0.05 level of significance. It implies that this domain can singly influence work motivation. Moreover, the R square value is .176 which implies that the organizational commitment influence work motivation of government employees by 17.6%. The variance of 82.4% is attributed to other factors not covered in the study. Organizational commitment influence work motivation as disclosed in the F –value of 12.491 with the p- value of .000 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significant. This implies further that organizational commitment has to do with the work motivation of employees. This finding is in parallel with the statement of Neyshabor, et al (2013) that employees with higher organizational commitment perform better and are highly motivated which are beneficial to the organization.

Organizational Commitment	Work Motivation			
	Beta	B	T-value	P-value
Continuance Commitment	.334	.428	4.75	.000
Normative Commitment	-.024	-.026	-.285	.776
R	.419			
R ²	.176 or 17.6%			
F-value	12.491			
P-value	.000			

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based from the findings, the researchers concluded that government employees disclosed high level of organizational commitment and work motivation. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation of government employees. Furthermore, organizational commitment significantly influences work motivation of government employees. Continuance commitment as domain of organizational commitment can singly influence work motivation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tom Miller. (2018, January 25). Local Government Employees Reveal What Makes for Job Satisfaction. Retrieved from <https://www.n-r-c.com/local-government-employees-reveal-what-makes-for-job-satisfaction/>
- [2] Anam Iqbal., Muhammad Sajid Tufail., and Rab Nawaz Lodhi. (2015, January). Employee Loyalty and Organizational Commitment in Pakistani Organizations. Retrieved from <http://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/Employee-Loyalty-and-Organizational-Commitment-in-Pakistani-Organizations.pdf>
- [3] Tung N. Nguyen., Khuong N. Mai., and Phuong V. Nguyen. (2014, March 1). Factors Affecting Employees' Organizational Commitment—A Study of Banking Staff in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. Retrieved from <http://www.joams.com/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=36&id=106>
- [4] Peace Irefin and Mohammed Ali Mechanic. (2014, March). Effect of Employee Commitment on Organizational Performance in Coca Cola Nigeria Limited Maiduguri, Borno State. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a3e8/545ddff660914975260533d1239b5cef3632.pdf>
- [5] Brian Francis Redmond. (2016, November 13). Work and Organizational Commitment. Retrieved from <https://wikispaces.psu.edu/display/PSYCH484/12.+Work+and+Organizational+Commitment>
- [6] Hardiyana, Aan and Yusup, Maulana and Sidharta, Iwan. (2016, January 15). Perception of Work and Commitment toward Employee Satisfaction on Non-Ministerial Government Agencies in Bandung Indonesia. Vol. 1, No. 6, January 2016, pp. 1-15. Retrieved from <https://mp.ra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/77075/>
- [7] Susan M. Heatfield. (2018, December 10). What People Want from Work. Motivation. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/what-people-want-from-work-motivation-1919051>
- [8] Linh Nguyen. (2017). The impact of employees' motivation on Organizational Effectiveness. Retrieved
- [9] Tom Miller. (2018, January 25). Local Government Employees Reveal What Makes for Job Satisfaction. Retrieved from <https://www.n-r-c.com/local-government-employees-reveal-what-makes-for-job-satisfaction/>
- [10] Anam Iqbal., Muhammad Sajid Tufail., and Rab Nawaz Lodhi. (2015, January). Employee Loyalty and Organizational Commitment in Pakistani Organizations. Retrieved from <http://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/Employee-Loyalty-and-Organizational-Commitment-in-Pakistani-Organizations.pdf>
- [11] Tung N. Nguyen., Khuong N. Mai., and Phuong V. Nguyen. (2014, March 1). Factors Affecting Employees' Organizational Commitment—A Study of Banking Staff in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. Retrieved from <http://www.joams.com/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=36&id=106>
- [12] Osmond Vitez. (2018). Difference Between Drive & Motivation. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/difference-between-drive-motivation-701.html>
- [13] Steve Crabtree. (2013, October 08). Worldwide, 13% of Employees Are Engaged at Work, Low workplace engagement offers opportunities to improve business outcomes. Retrieved from <https://news.gallup.com/poll/165269/worldwide-employees-engaged-work.aspx>
- [14] Catherine R. Curtis, Randall S. Upchurch & Denver E. Severt. (2009, August 05). Employee Motivation and Organizational Commitment: A Comparison of Tipped and Nontipped Restaurant Employees, *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, 10:3, 253-269, DOI: 10.1080/15256480903088469. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15256480903088469>
- [15] Kimberlee Leonard. (2018, June 27). Consequences of No Employee Motivation. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/consequences-employee-motivation-41238.html>
- [16] Stella Achieng' Odembo. (2013, November). Job satisfaction and employee performance within the telecommunication industry in kenya: a case of airtel kenya limited. Retrieved from <https://ir-library.ku.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/123456789/10135/Job%20Satisfaction%20and%20Employee%20Performance%20within%20the%20Telecommunication%20Industry%20in%20Kenya%20A%20Case%20of%20Airtel%20Kenya%20Limited.pdf;sequence=1>
- [17] Slack, Frederick J.; Orife, John N.; Anderson, Fred P. (2010, December). Effects of Commitment to Corporate Vision on Employee Satisfaction with their Organization: An Empirical Study in the United States. Retrieved from <https://www.questia.com/library/journal/1P3-2184287321/effects-of-commitment-to-corporate-vision-on-employee>
- [18] Wolff-Michael Roth & Pei-Ling Hsu. (2008). Interest and Motivation: A Cultural-Historical and Discursive Psychological Approach. Retrieved from <https://web.uvic.ca/~mroth/teaching/681-10Win/0107/Interest2.pdf>
- [19] Adrian Furnham. (2012). Money as a motivator. Retrieved from https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1057%2F9780230369764_41

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